

Effect of guanine alkylation on keto-enol tautomerism : A DFT study

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Abstract : Thermodynamic and kinetic driving force for keto-enol tautomerism in guanine, guanine-cytosine and alkylated guanine has been studied in gas as well as in aqueous phase using density functional theory (DFT). Variation of DFT based reactivity descriptors were observed along the IRC pathway. Energy barrier of the tautomerism is of almost same magnitude in guanine and alkylated guanine. No significant lowering in energy barrier is observed in alkylated guanine signifying the absence of kinetic driving force for enol formation. Thermochemical analysis confirmed a small barrier.

Keywords : Mustine, keto-enol tautomerism, alkylated guanine, DFT, reactivity descriptors.

Introduction

Since the earliest evidence of application of nitrogen mustards in cancer chemotherapy, mustine has always proven its worth as DNA inter-strand cross-linking agent over decades¹⁻⁷. It has been confirmed that its cytotoxicity is allied with its alkylating ability by means of preferential reaction with nucleophilic centres in DNA bases⁸⁻¹⁰. Mustine forms a very reactive aziridinium ion (Az^+) intermediate and preferential alkylation at the endocyclic nitrogen and exocyclic oxygen atoms of DNA bases is the suggested mechanism¹¹⁻¹⁶. Earlier works confirmed that out of different nucleophilic sites in DNA bases, N7 position of guanine is the most nucleophilic and was shown to be the most preferred site over others for alkylation^{12-14,17-20}. Mann made an explicit study on formation of Az^+ ion of nitrogen mustards using *ab-initio* dynamics²¹. Recently, Baik and his coworkers have studied the alkylation mechanism by nitrogen mustards²².

The incredible adaptability of the nucleic acid bases to form base pairs is facilitated by the presence of numerous H-bonded donor and acceptor groups and the bonding between the complementary bases are highly specific giving authentic information of DNA. The formation of the keto-enol tautomerism in DNA bases are responsible for many kind of mutations in DNA. This keto-enol tautomerism of the DNA base (guanine in GC) upshot the stability of canonical structure of the DNA strand. Gua-

nine of DNA is predominantly found in their keto form and forms base pair with cytosine as reported by Watson and Crick²³. They also reported that guanine in its enolic form may pair up with thymine in DNA and uracil in RNA causing hindrance in DNA replication due to mismatch in base pairing patterns²³. Many research findings have proved that under physiological conditions, guanine is mainly found in its neutral ketonic form²⁴.

The aziridinium ion intermediate is a positively charged species and alkylation at N7 of guanine which is adjacent to the carbonyl carbon makes the carbon center more positive and as a result the tautomeric equilibrium in guanine-cytosine base pair (GC) may be disturbed²⁵. Keto-enol tautomerism drew the interest of the scientific community in a number of occasions. Many research groups made explicit DFT study on keto-enol tautomerism in α -keto pyruvic acid²⁶, peptide groups²⁷, antioxidants²⁸, Schiff bases²⁹. Recently, Mishra and Agnihotri performed DFT study on different tautomers of the guanyl radical³⁰. Earlier, Persmark *et al.* made an experimental study on stability of alkylated DNA duplexes³¹. However, thermodynamic and kinetic aspects of the keto-enol tautomerism in alkylated guanine are not properly examined. Therefore, in our present investigation, we have laid emphasis in examining the kinetic as well thermodynamic driving force for keto-enol tautomerism in guanine (1), GC base pair (2) and alkylated guanine (3), Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Optimized structures of keto and enol form of guanine, GC and alkylated guanine.

Density functional theory (DFT) is an effective tool to study these aspects of chemical reactions and has been applied extensively to solve challenging problems in chemistry³². DFT based reactivity descriptors are widely used to provide proper explanation of problems and in last few decades a number of applications witnessed their applicability^{33,34}. It has been established that the study of global reactivity descriptors along the intrinsic reaction co-ordinate IRC is quite informative³⁵⁻³⁹.

Theoretical details of reactivity descriptors :

Conceptual density functional theory defines chemical potential, μ ⁴⁰ and global hardness, η ⁴¹ for an N-electron system with energy, E at constant external potential, $v(\vec{r})$, as the following first and second-order derivatives respectively

$$\mu = \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} \quad (1)$$

and

$$\eta = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial N} \right)_{v(\vec{r})} \quad (2)$$

Using finite difference approximation⁴² and Koopmans' theorem⁴³ μ and η can be expressed as :

$$\eta = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} - \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}}{2} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\mu = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} + \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}}{2} \quad (4)$$

Parr and co-workers proposed global electrophilicity (ω) as a measure of electrophilicity of a species as⁴⁴

$$\omega = \frac{\mu^2}{2\eta} \quad (5)$$

It is an important descriptor that successfully describe

stability of a species and have been used in a number of observations^{45,46}.

Computational details :

The geometrical minima of the species were optimized with 6-31+G(d) basis set with Becke three parameter exchange and Lee, Yang and Parr correlation functional, B3LYP in gas and aqueous phase. Real frequencies of the systems confirmed that they are at minima. The global reactivity descriptors η and ω were calculated using eqs. (3) and (4). The transition state (TS) of the tautomerism was obtained by QST3 method⁴⁷ and genuineness of the TS geometries was confirmed by an imaginary frequency of the vibrational mode. To check the consistency of our results, we performed single point calculations with a triple zeta basis set 6-311++G(d,p) using the same functional. Earlier work confirmed that the structure and stability of DNA is sensitive to solvation⁴⁸ and therefore we repeated our observations in aqueous phase using PCM (Polarizable Continuum Model)⁴⁹. All calculations were performed using Gaussian 09⁵⁰.

Results and discussion

Stability of free and alkylated species :

Table 1 presents η and ω of keto/enol forms of 1, 2 and 3 (see Fig. 1) at B3LYP/6-31+G(d) level of theory. It is evident from the table that, in gas phase keto form of guanine (1kg) is more stable ($\eta = 0.0981$, according to maximum hardness principle (MHP), maximum hardness leads to maximum stability) than the enol form (1eb) ($\eta = 0.0950$). To examine the stability of the species (keto

and enol forms) in a double stranded DNA, we have considered GC base pair (2) and calculated the reactivity indices. In case of 2, results are similar to that in guanine and keto form, 2kgc ($\eta = 0.0983$) is found to be more stable than to the enol form (2egc) ($\eta = 0.0948$). However, it is important to notice that in alkylated guanine, enol form (3aeg) is observed to be more stable ($\eta = 0.0681$) as compared to the keto form (3akg) ($\eta = 0.0678$). On the other hand, global philicity do not show the expected trend. Unexpectedly aqueous phase results do not agree with the gas phase trend, Table 1. Thus, the gas phase results agrees well with earlier works that suggest that on alkylation enol form becomes more stable^{25,31,51}. We observed similar trend at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory, Table 1.

As suggested in earlier works^{22,52}, the keto-enol tautomerism passes through a TS and to observe the variation in η , ω and μ philicity along the IRC, we obtained the transition state and calculated the indices for different conformations in both directions of the TS. Structures of the TS involved in keto-enol tautomerism in 1kg \rightarrow 1eg, 2kgc \rightarrow 2egc and 3akg \rightarrow 3aeg are shown in Fig. 2. In case of 1-TS, the O-H distance is observed to be 1.37 Å and N-H distance is 1.31 Å. However, in 2-TS, though O-H distance is almost similar as that in 1-TS, the N-H distance is observed to be a bit elongated (1.41 Å). Interestingly, coplanarity of the GC is maintained in the 2-TS. The 3-TS structural parameters are almost similar to 1-TS. This indicates that alkylation at N7 of guanine do not effect the TS structures.

Table 1. Variation of global hardness and global philicity of the species in gas and aqueous phase (values are in a.u.)

Tautomers	Level of theory							
	B3LYP/6-31+G(d)				B3LYP/6-311+G(d,p)			
	Gas phase		Aqueous phase		Gas phase		Aqueous phase	
	η	ω	η	ω	η	ω	η	ω
1kg	0.0981	0.0801	0.0983	0.0828	0.0963	0.0864	0.0976	0.0868
1eg	0.0950	0.0929	0.0948	0.0936	0.0949	0.0885	0.0942	0.0978
2kgc	0.0983	0.0828	0.0837	0.1044	0.0698	0.1172	0.0829	0.1097
2egc	0.0948	0.0936	0.0879	0.0985	0.0824	0.0953	0.0871	0.1035
3akg	0.0678	0.5087	0.0842	0.1418	0.0672	0.5219	0.0836	0.1468
3aeg	0.0681	0.5324	0.0815	0.1532	0.0676	0.5450	0.0810	0.1584

Fig. 2. Structures of the TS with some of the important parameters.

Fig. 3 shows the variation of η , μ and ω in $1\text{kg} \rightarrow 1\text{eg}$ along the IRC pathway in gas as well as in aqueous phases. It is evident that, in gas phase, we observed extremals for μ on the IRC path at d values -0.85 and $+1.24$, Figs. 3a and 3b. On the other hand, η shows extremals at $+0.62$

and $+2.06$ d values. Interestingly, variations of ω is not reverse to that of η , indicating that maximum hardness principle (MHP) and minimum electrophilicity principle (MEP) are not applicable in this case. Importantly none of the indices shows minima or maxima at the TS; however, a rapid variation around the TS is observed. Earlier, Chamorro *et al.* also observed sharp variation in global reactivity descriptors around the TS³⁹ for $\text{HCN}-\text{CNH}$ reaction. In aqueous phase, μ and ω show similar trend as that in gas phase, however, maximum at $+0.62$ vanishes in case of η , Fig. 3c and 3d.

Results in Fig. 3 explain the variation of reactivity descriptors in keto-enol tautomerism in a single strand DNA (as we have considered guanine only). It would be worth mentioning that tautomerism in double stranded DNA might be different from that in a single stranded DNA. Thus, to mimic the environment of a double strand DNA, we observed the variations of the indices in GC base pair, $2\text{kgc} \rightarrow 2\text{egc}$, Fig. 4. On contrary, the gas phase parameters observed in case of $2\text{kgc} \rightarrow 2\text{egc}$ are not consistent with the results of $1\text{kg} \rightarrow 1\text{eg}$, Fig. 4a and 4b. From Figs. 4a and 4b, a marked variation in the variation of the reactivity indices is observed in presence of cytosine. We observed two extremals of μ on the IRC path and are at d values -0.21 and $+1.450$; η shows four extremals at -0.93 , $+0.21$, $+1.03$ and $+1.66$. Variation in ω is similar to that of η and exhibit extremals at -0.83 , $+0.10$, $+1.04$ and $+1.99$. Interestingly, a rapid variation of the indices near the TS is observed. In aqueous phase, number of extremals is more than that in gas phase; μ exhibit four extremals; for η , we observed seven extremals and variation in ω is similar to that of η , Figs. 4c and 4d. It is important to note that in aqueous phase we observed an extremal at the TS, Figs. 4c and 4d, which clearly indicates the effect of solvent on the IRC pathway. Earlier, Deepa *et al.* studied keto-enol tautomerism in GC base pair⁵³. They observed a prominent effect on interaction energy on addition of water molecules to GC base pair. However, effect on the reaction pathway was not investigated. Our results clearly indicate the effect of solvent phase on the IRC pathway.

Fig. 3. Variation of (a) global hardness and chemical potential, (b) global hardness and philicity of guanine (1kg→1eg) along the IRC pathway corresponding to keto-enol tautomerism in (c) gas phase and (d) in aqueous phase.

Fig. 5 shows the variation of η , μ and ω of alkylated guanine, 3akg→3aeg along the IRC pathway in gas as well as in aqueous phases. From Fig. 5, it is apparent that the pattern of variation of the indices in 3akg→3aeg is different to that of 1kg→1eg or 2kgc→2egc. We observed only one minimum for μ at d value +0.83, for η , the minimum is located at the TS and +0.62 for ω , Figs. 5a and 5b. On the other hand, in aqueous phase, extremals for η , μ and ω are observed at d value +0.82, Figs. 5c and 5d. Thus, we observed a complicated variation of the indices in case of 3akg→3aeg.

Energy barrier of the tautomerism :

Calculation of energy barrier of a reaction is quite

informative in predicting the kinetic driving force of a reaction. To quantify the energy barrier and effect of alkylation on the kinetic driving force, we calculated the energy barrier for the keto-enol tautomerism in gas as well in aqueous phase for 1kg→1eg, 2kgc→2egc and 3akg→3aeg, at B3LYP/6-31+G(d) level of theory, Table 2. It is important to note that energy barrier for keto-enol reaction in guanine (1kg→1eg) is quite high, 33.03 kcal/mol in gas phase and 31.91 kcal/mol in aqueous phase; solvent polarity is thus imparting no significant effect on enol formation. In case of GC (2kgc→2egc), this barrier is 31.37 kcal/mol in gas phase and 30.01 kcal/mol in aqueous phase. In case of alkylated guanine (3akg→3aeg),

Fig. 4. Variation of (a) global hardness and chemical potential, (b) global hardness and philicity of GC (2kgc→2egc) along IRC pathway corresponding to keto-enol tautomerism (in gas phase).

this barrier is even higher, 34.53 kcal/mol in gas phase and 33.02 kcal/mol in aqueous phase. Little lower energy barrier in aqueous phase in all three cases might results a faster keto to enol conversion in aqueous phase compared to gas phase. However, we do not observe enhanced in kinetic driving force alkylated guanine. We observe similar trend in 6-311++G(d,p) level of theory, Table 2.

Thermodynamic analysis :

To comprehend the thermodynamic driving force of the tautomerism, Fig. 6, we calculated enthalpy and Gibbs free energy of the tautomerism; values at the two level of theories are summarized in Table 3. It is interesting to note that gas phase enthalpy of keto-enol tautomerism in 1kg→1eg is quite small and is endothermic (enthalpy is +1.98 kcal/mol). However, in case of 3akg→3aeg, enthalpy is a bit higher enthalpy (+4.72 kcal/mol) is observed. In aqueous phase, the observed values of enthalpy

Table 2. Activation energy for different keto-enol tautomerism (values are in kcal/mol)

Tautomerism	Level of theory			
	B3LYP/6-31+G(d)		B3LYP/6311+G(d,p)	
	Gas phase	Aqueous phase	Gas phase	Aqueous phase
1kg→1eg	33.03	31.91	36.29	35.15
2kgc→2egc	31.37	30.01	35.53	34.91
3akg→3aeg	34.53	33.02	37.81	36.22

in 1kg→1eg and 3akg→3aeg are 7.96 kcal/mol and 8.76 kcal/mol respectively. In case of 2kgc→2egc, enthalpy of the reaction is observed to be 14.18 kcal/mol in gas phase and 14.98 kcal/mol in aqueous phase. In all the three cases we observed a very small ΔH values. Interestingly, comparatively higher value of ΔH for 2kgc→2egc inferred that the tautomerism is difficult in double strand DNA than single strand DNA. Similar trend is also observed in ΔG value, Table 3. Thus one might not ruled out the thermodynamic driving force for the tautome-

Fig. 5. Variation of (a) global hardness and chemical potential, (b) global hardness and global philicity of alkylated guanine (3akg→3aeg) along IRC pathway corresponding to keto-enol tautomerism (in gas phase).

Table 3. Thermochemical parameters for different keto-enol tautomerism (values are in kcal/mol)

Tautomerism	Level of theory							
	B3LYP/6-31+G(d)				B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p)			
	Gas phase		Aqueous phase		Gas phase		Aqueous phase	
	ΔH	ΔG	ΔH	ΔG	ΔH	ΔG	ΔH	ΔG
1kg→1eg	1.98	2.16	7.96	8.09	1.22	1.38	7.11	7.23
2kgc→2egc	14.18	12.84	14.98	15.30	13.23	12.23	14.71	13.27
3akg→3aeg	4.72	4.95	8.76	9.00	4.01	4.21	7.96	8.04

rism. Consistent results were observed at B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) level of theory, Table 3. In all the species we observed thermodynamic stability of the keto-form over the enol form and is consistent with the earlier results⁵³.

Conclusion

In this article we have examined the kinetic and thermodynamic driving force for the keto-enol tautomerism in free guanine, GC base pair and alkylated guanine. We observed no kinetic driving force for the keto-enol tautomerism in guanine, GC or alkylated guanine. Interest-

Fig. 6. Energy profile diagram for keto-enol tautomerism.

ingly small thermodynamic barrier (ΔH and ΔG of the reaction) indicates that the thermodynamic factors may be helpful to the keto-enol transformations. We observed sharp variations in the reactivity indices along the IRC pathway and are consistent with earlier work by Chattaraj *et al.*³⁹. Solvent polarity imparts little effect on the thermochemistry of the tautomerism; however, it effects the variation of reactivity indices along the IRC. Presence of cytosine makes the IRC pathway more complicated. On the other hand alkylation at guanine exerts no effect on the IRC pathway. Our findings advocate that keto to enol conversion may take place favourably single strand DNA.

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